

Destination Earth

Building a highly accurate digital twin of the Earth

Stay informed of key milestones, events and engagement opportunities by subscribing to the DestinE community

destination-earth.eu

POLICYMAKERS

Boosting policy effectiveness

DestinE is a flagship initiative of the European Commission that will support climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies by developing a full digital twin of the Earth. This new information system will encompass unprecedented levels of detail, quality and interactivity, to support policymakers to better respond and adapt to environmental challenges posed by extreme events and climate change.

Knowledge gained from DestinE simulations will enable policymakers to better understand the impact of potential climate crisis mitigation strategies and make data-driven, effective policy decisions. Combining data from various sources will bring new insights and perspectives on the potential impacts of proposed policies and decisions.

Stakeholders across all policy levels

Local

Regional

International

Continental

Ecoregional

Global

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DestinE will foster the implementation of the EU Digital Strategy and the Green Deal target of a climate-neutral Europe by 2050 by leveraging digital technology to enable accurate and actionable adaptation strategies and mitigation measures to:

Anticipate both natural disasters and man-made environmental damage.

Enable investigating what if scenarios to understand consequences of adaptation choices and explore possible future evolutions of our planet.

Understand the socio-economic effects of climate change.

Help communities adapt to climate change related challenges.

Destination Earth Components

DestinE Platform

User's entry point to the DestinE system, offering evidence-based decision-making tools, applications and services, based on an open, flexible, and secure cloud-based computing infrastructure.

Data Lake

Data access harmonisation of digital twins data and federated providers such as ESA, EUMETSAT, ECMWF, Copernicus and many other sources. Big data processing capabilities provided to allow computing in proximity to the data.

Digital Twins and Digital Twin Engine

Digital twins of different aspects of the earth system based on the fusion of cutting-edge simulations and observations, orchestrated by the Digital Twin Engine that provides a software infrastructure for digital twin data access, workflows and interoperability and data production and handling.

